

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW PREVALENCE OF POLY CYSTIC
OVARIAN SYNDROME AMONG STUDENTS OF A
TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL****Dr. Mehwish Liaquat, Dr. Misbah Haider, Dr. Atika Javed**
Allama Iqbal Medical College lahore**Abstract:**

Objective of the study: Pakistan already has the highest number of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus worldwide. The rapid increase in the incidence of obesity in children is the main reason for the increase in insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia and polycystic ovary syndrome. The prevalence of this syndrome in our community remains unknown.

Objective: the study was conducted to determine the prevalence of PCOS among students in Punjab ,Pakistan due to the low prevalence of PCOS prevalence data in the state. We sought to establish prevalence among students aged 17 to 23 in a tertiary care university hospital.

Materials and methods: a cross-sectional study with sample size was conducted 246. Students aged 17 to 23 were randomly selected from various medical and paramedical courses. The presence of hyperandrogenic characteristics and menstrual irregularities was evaluated and physically examined to validate the self-scoring mFG score. The PCOS diagnosis was based on the Rotterdam criteria.

Results: 79 students (32.11%) met the criteria for the diagnosis of polycystic ovary syndrome. 13 students (5.2%) had a history of thyroid dysfunction. The other clinical features of hyperandrogenism in PCOS patients were oily skin (13.82%), acne (8.53%), increased hair growth (5.69%), male thinning of hair (9.75%) and a high level of intolerance to cold and heat (3.25%) and galactorrhoea (0%).

Conclusion: PCOS can be considered as a precursor syndrome that can be useful for the early diagnosis of the risk of high-grade diseases in girls and adolescent women in their twenties when tested.

Keywords: PCOS, Adolescent, Risk factors

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Please cite t h i s article in press Mehwish Liaquat et al., **Study To Know Prevalence Of Poly Cystic Ovarian Syndrome Among Students Of A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(11).

INTRODUCTION:

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common endocrine disorders in women. The prevalence of polycystic ovary syndrome in endocrine disorders is between 2.2 and 26%. 1-6 There are many interaction factors that lead to clinical and / or biochemical hyperandrogenism. Symptoms of PCOS appear slowly and these features coincide with changes in the normal development of puberty. Therefore, these subtle features may not be recognized at an early stage and may be responsible for the failure to identify the disorder in girls. Women with PCOS have an increased risk of obstructive sleep apnea, infertility, compromised uterine bleeding, metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease, depression and some cancers. Preventive measures such as exercises, healthy nutrition, meditation exercises, sedative exercises to reduce stress levels, etc. They play an important role in reducing the complications of PCOS. Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a serious health risk for both mother and fetus. The diagnosis of PCOS at an early stage of life may therefore help prevent these complications of maternal and child health, which appear to affect two of the eight disorders

Objectives of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) .13 The first step towards an early and accurate diagnosis is to determine the prevalence rate of the disease among the different types (age and ethnicity) of the population . The frequency of adiposity in children is rapidly increasing, leading to metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia, insulin resistance and polycystic ovary syndrome . Prevalence in Asian countries appears to be lower, with a reported prevalence of 2.4% in China¹ and 6.3% in Sri Lanka²³ (Rotterdam criteria).

Given the causes mentioned above and the fact that the prevalence of this syndrome remains unknown in our community, we have tried to find out. The prevalence of female doctors, dentists, nurses and paramedics between the ages of 17 and 23 in a university hospital in Punjab ,Pakistan

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross-sectional study was conducted at a university hospital for tertiary care in Punjab ,Pakistan. The approval of the institutional ethics committee was obtained before the trial. Based on the predicted prevalence of 20% and a 95% confidence level, the sample size for this project was calculated as 246. Students aged 17 to 23 years were randomly selected from several lots and medical and paramedical courses. Although they were students of a higher education institution in a given area, they represented a larger geographical area, since they came from urban, semi-urban and rural areas nearby. Subjects then received questionnaires with questions on the presence of

hyperandrogenic characteristics and menstrual disorders (amenorrhea / oligomenorrhea). All subjects were physically examined to validate the subject's self-rated mFG rating. The PCOS diagnosis was based on the Rotterdam criteria. According to the Rotterdam guidelines (2003), the patient should have two of three criteria: chronic oligo or anovulation, clinical and / or biochemical signs of hyperandrogenism, polycystic ovaries. The exclusion of other causes of androgen excess and anovulatory infertility is required. The Rotterdam criteria are based on the principles of the modified Ferriman Gallwey rating, the criteria for ultrasound and the evaluation of anovulation. The Ferriman Gallwey score of 8 or higher defines the population of women with hirsutism.¹⁵ The ultrasound criterion defines that the polycystic ovary has 12 or more follicles of 2-9 mm in size and / or an increased ovarian volume > 10 cm³ , 16 Menstrual disorders in PCOS are generally in the form of oligomenorrhea (less than eight menstruation per year or menstrual bleeding that occurs at intervals of more than 35 days) .¹⁷ Female students between the ages of 17 and 23 study medicine or paramedicina. The university course and availability for ultrasound examination were included in the study. Consent was obtained both in the questionnaire and at the time of the ultrasounds.

RESULTS:

79 students (32.11%) met the criteria to be diagnosed as polycystic ovarian syndrome. The demographic profile and the average age of the menstruation start of the students are listed in the table

1. The percentage of students meeting the Rotterdam criteria is shown in Table 2. The total number of students with a previous PCOS diagnosis was 10.16%. Previously, two students were diagnosed with PCOS, but now they did not meet the Rotterdam criteria because the ultrasound criteria were not met (absence of cysts in the ovaries that meet the criteria). 13 students (5.2%) had a history of thyroid dysfunction. Number of students, among those who have thyroid (as denominator); now diagnosed with PCOS was 61.5%. The other clinical features of hyperandrogenism in patients with PCOS were oily skin (13.82%), acne (8.53%), increased hair growth (5.69%) and thinning of the male hair (9.75%), high grade Cold and heat intolerance (3.25%) and galactorrhoea (0%). The other hyperandrogenic features were not considered in the diagnosis of PCOS because there is no standardized method (such as the Ferriman Gallwey method for hirsutism) that uses these features to meet the Rotterdam criteria for clinical hyperandrogenism. None of the students presented a personal or family

history of congenital adrenal hyperplasia or late-onset galactorrhea.

Table 1: Demographic profile of PCOS students

Demographic profile and mFG score	With PCOS	Without PCOS
Age	18.91± 1.69	19.12 ± 2.04
BMI	23.49 ± 3.89	22.28 ± 3.12
mFG score	8.51 ± 0.58	4.53± 0.28
Average age of onset of menstruation	12.71± 0.60	13.23± 0.68

Data are expressed as Mean± SD

Table 2: Percentage of students who met the Rotterdam's criteria

Clinical Features	Proportion of students
Irregular periods	28.86%
Cyst or increased stroma in ovaries	34.14%
Hirsutism (mFG)	24.79%
Both menstrual irregularity and cyst in ovaries	23.57%
Both cyst in ovaries and hirsutism	15.04%
Both menstrual irregularity and hirsutism	9.75%
Menstrual irregularity, cyst in ovaries and hirsutism	8.5%

Data are expressed in percentage

DISCUSSION:

The average age of students with and without PCOS did not make a big difference. Well there

There appears to be no difference in the incidence of PCOS in the different ages between 17 and 23 years. The average BMI of persons with PCOS is slightly higher (1.21) than those without PCOS. The average mFG score shows an average score increase of 3.98 for persons with PCOS compared to persons without PCOS. Among the three Rotterdam criteria, the presence of follicles or an increase in the stroma in the ovaries is the most common, indicating that this is a common event. The percentage of students with only one menstrual disorder with cysts (15.85%) is higher than the percentage of those who have only the other two combinations (6.5% and 1.2%), with one of them Have irregularity Menstruation has more of a cyst and vice versa. About 10.16% of the students had already received a PCOS diagnosis, but the prevalence was 32.11%, indicating that screening and early diagnosis and awareness of the condition are needed. Approximately 61.5% of students with thyroid disorders also have a PCOS. Therefore, there is more than half the likelihood that adolescent girls will have PCOS if diagnosed with thyroid dysfunction. Similar reports were reported in a survey of 728 women whose prevalence was 8.7% according to NIH criteria and 17.8% according to the Rotterdam criteria.²²

PCOS is one of the most common endocrine disorders in women, but diagnosis, management and complications have not been standardized. Hyperandrogenism and menstrual disorders are the most common symptoms in patients with PCOS,

but these symptoms are not an absolute prerequisite for the diagnosis of PCOS. Similarly, the ultrasound detection of polycystic ovaries as a diagnostic marker is not very meaningful. The percentage prevalence of PCOS was 32.11%, which is comparable to some other studies.^{2,12,24}. The prevalence of PCOS in young women may be due to unhealthy eating habits such as junk food, lack of exercise and physical inactivity. Childhood childhood obesity may lead to insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome later in life. Today, people have to take care of themselves and reduce stress. I know that students should be encouraged to follow stress reduction techniques, such as yoga and meditation, and to change their lifestyle. Studies conducted on the family PCOS. The mFG score is subjective and in this study; the subject, the student, the subject, the subject, the subject, the subject of the scope.

CONCLUSION:

The percentage prevalence of PCOS at a tertiary medical college in Allama Iqbal Medical College for students aged 17 to 23 was set at 32.11%. Now that it has been found that the percentage prevalence is higher than in the previously cited studies, and the future complications are associated with serious consequences Morbidity (microdiabetic and macrovascular complications; neonatal complications in the birth of a GDM patient); The disease should be given greater importance by screening and early detection. This should be followed by advice on lifestyle changes. Awareness of the existence of a condition called PCOS in public is low alarming and it is our duty to educate the masses about the complications involved and the need for prevention. However, the

percentage of people diagnosed with PCOS at this time who experience complications in the future should first be evaluated to determine if a diagnosis at this age is a predictable value for assessing the risk of complications such as infertility; Diabetes, metabolic syndrome, etc. in the future. This study may then be followed by a cohort study in which we can monitor these long-term students to observe and find out how many of them will develop complications in the future. Therefore, it can be determined whether and to what extent a PCOS diagnosis at the age of 17 to 23 years can actually predict the occurrence of complications.

Once this determines; if the predicted value is high; With this PCOS diagnostic criterion, a PCOS screening can be performed for all adolescents over the age of 18 years. This would therefore reduce the incidence of morbidity associated with the disease.

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